

Image Geolocalization via Combined Classification and Regression

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Abstract—This paper presents a geolocation system to assist in identifying the location in images associated with illicit activities, thereby reducing investigation time for authorities. The system is implemented as a multi-agent system. The geolocalisation is performed based on image analysis, which involves both image classification and regression of the geographical coordinates. The final result is obtained by fusing both results. The classification model is based on the EfficientNet architecture. The evaluation is performed on a dataset with images from Romania collected from Google Street View. Moreover, the best version of the model succeeds in solving difficult classification tasks, correctly identifying the answer among two or more similar counties in 80% of the cases. Alternatively, from a regression point of view, the predicted coordinates are at most 80 km away from the ground truth location in over 80% of the evaluation cases. By employing various data augmentation techniques, such as noise addition or severe compression, a model robust to potential adversarial interference was achieved.

Index Terms—geolocalization, classification, regression, EfficientNet, ArcFace.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, law enforcement cannot be effective without paying attention to the content that is shared through digital means. The fight against illicit activities evolved over the last few decades. Now, besides the physical world, there is a continuous battle in the digital world as well. The same platforms that enable us to stay connected or to more easily access all of the world’s knowledge can become key tools for malicious actors. In this context, artificial intelligence solutions would be able to assist digital forensics investigations with accurate and efficient predictions. Criminals consistently post images or videos of their illicit activities. These pieces of data are analyzed to gather evidence and, ultimately, identify individuals and the places they are operating in. Geolocating from images with AI solutions can become an important step in the digital investigation procedure because it could accelerate decision making and incident resolution.

Designing a system for the task of geolocation, in this setting, comes with its own set of challenges. Firstly, illicit media might be deliberately degraded (e.g., pixelated, cropped, or compressed), making it harder to extract identifiable details.

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Also, public available datasets (e.g., Google Street View) might not generalize well to data that may feature non-public or rarely photographed locations. Also, misidentifications could lead to wrong allocation of investigation resources. The solution would be to associate a confidence alongside what the model predicts. In this context, artificial intelligence solutions would be able to assist digital forensics investigations with accurate and efficient predictions.

The paper proposes a system for image geolocalization that provides an approximate location from images, helping the authorities in their search for bad actors. The system will provide a hybrid solution by combining image classification and coordinates regression through a multi-agent system. Tests will be made on images from Romania since we can employ fine-grained recognition techniques to discriminate between very similar but yet distinctive regions of the country.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents a set of existing models for geolocation. Section 3 describes the proposed system. Evaluation is given in Section 4. Conclusions and future work are given in Section 5.

II. RELATED WORK

Several works have tackled image geolocalization without the purpose of obtaining an assistive system for law enforcement, but rather as exploratory work about what is the limit of deep learning models when it comes to identifying locations on the whole planet or smaller regions. IM2GPS [1] is one of the first work that aim to solve image geolocalization. The proposed solution involves a retrieval-based approach, where a query image is compared against a database of reference images. The comparison is performed through similarity of visual features chosen manually and not through embeddings like more modern projects. Other, more recent retrieval-based solutions focus on restricted versions of the problem, attempting accurate geolocalization within cities or countries.

Paper [2] outlined geolocalization as a classification problem, subdividing the surface of the earth into a set of geographical cells which make up the target classes. At inference time, their deep learning model, PlaNet, outputs a discrete probability distribution over the earth, assigning each geographical cell a likelihood that the input photo was taken inside it. Our baseline model will also treat the problem as a classification one, employing newer architectures with the

purpose of establishing a strong starting point for subsequent improvements.

Paper [3], using the same classification view, propose a new partitioning scheme where the cells are not rectangular or arbitrarily shaped. Instead, the partitioning considers more natural transitions in visual features, such as landscape or sovereignty (e.g. different countries or regions in the same country could be distinguished through traffic signs, road markings, language or other contextual clues). Moreover, they make use of hierarchical knowledge already provided by a reverse geocoder to further enhance the performance of their solution. In this project, we also adopt territorial boundaries, namely US state borders or Romanian counties.

More recently, PIGEON [4] emerged as a versatile geolocalization model that employs an extensive bag of tricks to achieve state-of-the-art performance. It is a hybrid, multi-modal approach that uses a fine-tuned CLIP vision encoder to obtain features which are then passed to a classification head for identifying a corresponding geocell. To further refine the prediction, they cluster all points in each geocell and create location clusters whose representations are the average embeddings of the cluster members. At inference time, the location cluster of a query image is the one that minimizes the euclidean distance in the embedding space. Once the cluster is determined, they further refine the guess by choosing a single best element from that cluster and assigning its coordinates as the final output. This refinement doesn't use only the clusters from the most likely predicted geocell, but the top k ones.

All the previous works target global geolocalization and do not offer an overview about what happens with their solutions when applied to a more restricted range. This is relevant because a smaller area is usually less diverse and, consequently, harder to discriminate. Nonetheless, their techniques prove very powerful and we design experiments to investigate if they are as useful in our context.

Moreover, this reduced scope places us in a favourable position to use fine-grained recognition methods to better distinguish very similar regions.

When focusing on the specific usecase of law enforcement, existing works can be split into 2 main directions of research: metadata-oriented or visual-based [5].

The former category gives special attention to metadata attached to images. In an adversarial context, a bad actor could try to alter the geographical information to not match with the actual location or to even remove this piece of information altogether. Paper [6] is one of the works that employ metadata processing in order to reveal potential alterations. Specifically, their framework is designed to validate the truthfulness of the time and location metadata by comparing the claimed values present in the file with estimated ones through sun position and shadow estimation algorithms. However, this approach operates under several restricting assumptions, one of which is considering that the visual content is not modified and, if that would be the case, they can reliably detect it with existing anti-forgery solutions. Similarly, paper [7] created a method to predict whether the visual content correctly matches the time

and location metadata, additionally using corresponding satellite images. Their CNN-based architecture consists in several branches of encoders, one for each modality. The features are aggregated and used to obtain a consistency label, indicating the presence or absence of any tampering. Moreover, for explainability purposes, they insert auxiliary branches that have the task to predict attributes (i.e. 40-dimensional arrays of characteristic indicators) of either the ground-level image or the satellite image. Solution from [8] propose a solution that closely resembles the previously outlined system. Given the geolocation and the visual information, they use time-focused multi-scale consistency losses to assess if the estimated month, week and hour match the expected values.

The latter category of solutions do not use metadata information on the input side, as it was highlighted previously. However, they aim to derive geolocation solely by inspecting the visual content. For example, research from [9] employ a retrieval-based approach, which leverages already available public data from geographic information systems. Alternatively, in [11] it is adopted a different approach, where they link people's appearance and geographical location. Their solution, GPS2Face, is a conditional generative model, producing human faces from location metadata. The effectiveness of their model confirms that geolocalization could be done by using a wide range of visual cues.

Ultimately, retrieval-based techniques [1], [4], [9] rely on large reference databases but they can offer better out-of-the box interpretability by considering retrieved samples as influential examples. At the same time, classification-based techniques [2], [3] are more space efficient but less interpretable.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

We propose a system for image based geolocalization by combining classification and regression that is suitable for more constrained deployment scenarios. In case of classification, the output consists in a probability distribution over geocells (i.e. Romanian counties), from which we derive the final prediction as the label corresponding to the largest probability. In case of regression, the output consists in a 2-dimensional vector representing estimated latitude and longitude for the provided input.

In order to facilitate the integration of the system into real-world operational contexts, the system is conceptualized as a Multi-Agent System. The proposed architecture consists in (Fig. 1):

- 1) The Preprocessing Agent, which receives raw images and it is responsible for performing preprocessing operations including resizing, normalization, augmentation. The input images are resized to square images with various sizes to assess to impact of resolution to the final performance. Due to the fact that we are using images with non-square resolution, the images were either center cropped or padded to a square before resizing to one of the tested resolutions. The augmentation comprises horizontal flip with 0.5 probability, one of

brightness/contrast adjustment or gamma correction and Cutout of 1 to 6 holes, biggest mask having 1/16 of the image resolution. Moreover, we employ weather transforms, noise insertion or compression in order to improve robustness to interventions that adversaries may perform. Finally, the images are normalized using the ImageNet statistics (i.e. per-channel mean and standard deviation).

- 2) The Classification Agent and the Regression Agent serve as parallel inference modules. The Classification Agent attempts to determine the most probable region (e.g., county) based on visual similarities. In contrast, the Regression Agent estimates geographic coordinates. These two agents work independently.
- 3) The Decision Agent, which consolidates results and computes confidence levels. It integrates both outputs by evaluating the consistency between the classification and regression predictions. First the predicted coordinates from the regression model are checked against the polygonal boundaries of the classified region. Then the following rules are applied:
 - If the points lie within the predicted region, the system accepts the classification with high confidence.
 - If the coordinate lies outside the classified region, the system computes the geographic distance between the coordinate and the centroid of the predicted region using.
 - If the distance is below a predefined threshold (e.g., 50 km), the classification is accepted with lower confidence. If the coordinate is significantly distant from the classified region, the system searches all known region centroids to identify the closest match.
 - If this closest region differs from the classifier’s prediction, the sample is flagged as ambiguous and potentially routed for manual review.

Fig. 1. System architecture.

IV. EVALUATION RESULTS

Evaluation is performed for both image classification and coordinates regression with the purpose of designing a solution suitable even for more constrained deployment scenarios.

We created a new dataset GeoguessRO, a version of DeepGeo b16 composed only with locations from Romania (from Google Street View). There are 95900 locations available, with very small imbalance between different counties. Each sample

contains 4 rectified, 400x250 Street View images taken from a certain location, with the first one always being oriented along the road. For each county, the territory is uniformly covered by the data points present in GeoguessRO, offering a mix of rural and urban settings. Unlike DeepGeo which requires an additional filtering step, GeoguessRO samples have been selected such that each one is at least 500m away from any other one, thus mitigating any data leakage earlier in the data processing pipeline.

A. Image Geolocalization through Classification

Image geolocalization is evaluated using two cases: by image classification and by retrieval-based classification.

1) *Image Geolocalisation*: The primary classifier architecture consists of a feature backbone and a classification head. The backbone is ablated between different model versions/sizes of the EfficientNet [12] family: B0 (small), B3 (medium) and B7 (large). The classification head maps the embedding provided by the backbone to the N logits corresponding to each geocell (N=42 Romanian counties). In order to alleviate the potential for overfitting, the backbone uses a nonzero DropPath probability and the last linear layer is preceded by a dropout layer. The DropPath probability is set to different values for each model version according to timm implementation guidelines while the dropout is fixed to 0.2. Unless otherwise stated, the backbone version is EfficientNet-B3 because it provided a good balance between training speed, inference speed and predictive accuracy.

The performance of diverse combinations of image resolution and model size can be inspected in Table I. Thus, higher-resolution inputs consistently improve the classification accuracy, confirming the intuition that higher resolution provides enhanced ability to distinguish very similar locations. The same trend is observed when keeping the resolution fixed and varying the model size. The improvements in the 2 dimensions are additive, due to the fact that moving to both higher resolutions and larger models results in performance gains. However, these improvements enter the diminishing return regime. From a practical point of view, for resource-constrained environments, smaller models at medium resolution (e.g., EfficientNet-B3 at 384) could provide a balance between accuracy and computational cost. Moreover, for applications requiring the highest accuracy, the largest model (B7) with the highest resolution (640) is optimal, albeit more computationally expensive.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCES (%) FOR DIFFERENT EFFICIENTNET TYPES AND INPUT RESOLUTIONS

Resolution / Model	EfficientNet-B0	EfficientNet-B3	EfficientNet-B7
256	71.77	73.23	75.56
384	73.46	74.61	76.32
512	74.65	76.85	78.17

For inputs we considered 4 types of formats:

- 1) one image per location

- 2) 4 images for a given location can be concatenated along the channel dimension, producing a 12-channel input (early fusion/integration).
- 3) each of the 4 images can be processed independently by the feature extractor and the resulting embeddings can be pooled together (e.g. concatenated, averaged, etc.) (medium integration).
- 4) all 4 images are concatenated into a 2x2 grid, similar to the mosaicing used by YOLO models. If the original views have resolution $N \times N$, this would yield a $2N \times 2N$ image. If the value $2N$ is reasonable enough from an operational point of view (i.e. not prone to out of memory errors), then this combined image is not resized.

Table II shows these evaluations. Firstly, the biggest difference in performance stems from using all 4 images for a given location instead of one. This should be expected due to the fact that the former can provide more information to the model (e.g. possibly street signs, extended landscape view, etc.). When differentiating between the 3 versions that use the same number of images, no significant improvement in accuracy can be observed for one against the others. However, regarding the operational metrics, medium integration has a latency penalty due to the sequential processing of each view.

TABLE II
UPDATED COMPARISON OF GEOLOCATION FORMATS BY ACCURACY AND LATENCY

Format	Accuracy (\uparrow)	Latency (\downarrow)
1 image/location	62.61	40.67
Early integration	68.52	54.33
Medium integration	73.23	132.81
Mosaic image	70.48	67.12

The overall performance of the classifier is quite good. Nonetheless, we can inspect failure cases (i.e. misclassified examples) to better understand where the model struggles and how we could improve the solution. When the model is wrong, the most often encountered case is that the predicted geocell is usually a neighbour of the ground truth one (Table III).

TABLE III
TOP 5 MOST CONFUSED COUNTY PAIRS

Confused Counties	Number of Confusions
Ilfov, București	52
Ialomița, Călărași	51
Prahova, Dâmbovița	46
Vaslui, Iași	46
Vâlcea, Gorj	45

For Romania, the region-wise mistakes are not as frequent (Fig. 2). The diagonal blocks pattern is not as obvious in this case, highlighting less distinguishability.

The best two scores correspond to Tulcea, due to a considerable amount of images from the Danube Delta, a very distinctive place, and Braila, due to an artifact of the collected

Fig. 2. Full confusion matrix (left) and processed confusion matrix with main diagonal zeroed out for visibility of the other elements (right). The counties have been reordered according to proximity.

images (Fig. 3). Unlike the neighbouring counties, Braila has a different distribution of when the images were captured and, consequently, what type of camera was used at that time. The model was able to pick up the variation produced by the different sensors.

Fig. 3. Per class accuracies for the classification model with medium integration, 4 views of 256x256.

A better picture of the performance can be created by employing additional metrics, such as precision, recall, F1-score or MAP@k (mean average precision). The obtained values indicate that the model performs consistently high for most classes (Tables IV).

TABLE IV
DETAILED QUANTITATIVE RESULTS FOR CLASSIFIER MODEL. INPUT SIZE: 512x512, MEDIUM INTEGRATION, EFFICIENTNET-B3 BACKBONE

Top-k	Accuracy (\uparrow)	Precision (\uparrow)	Recall (\uparrow)	F1 (\uparrow)	MAP@k
1	76.85	77.01	76.85	76.79	—
2	86.77	86.87	86.77	86.75	—
5	94.38	94.40	94.38	94.37	83.97

2) *Retrieval-based classification*: Instead of tackling this problem from a standard classification point of view, by using ArcFace [13], the embeddings produced by the backbone model exist in a more regularized latent space. In this setting, the classification is done according to details presented next. Every image of training set is passed through the backbone and the embedding is saved. For each test-time input, the cosine similarity between the embedding of the current input and each indexed embedding is computed. The final prediction is the

label associated with the indexed example most similar to the current input. For top k most probable labels, we pass through the list of examples (sorted by cosine similarity in decreasing order) and select the first k unique labels encountered.

Based on the results from Table V, ArcFace is consistently outperforming the standard classifier across all configurations. This indicates that the ArcFace approach benefits from the additional discriminative feature learning, due to the specialized form of the loss function. Moreover, similar to the previous results, ArcFace-trained models benefit from larger resolutions and backbones, albeit with diminishing returns and more demanding computational cost.

TABLE V
COMPARISON OF CLASSIFIER AND ARCFACE ACCURACIES ACROSS RESOLUTIONS AND EFFICIENTNET BACKBONES. FORMAT: CLASSIFIER / ARCFACE ACCURACY (%)

Resolution / Model	EfficientNet-B0	EfficientNet-B3	EfficientNet-B7
256	71.77 / 73.74	73.23 / 75.71	75.56 / 77.52
384	73.46 / 75.38	74.61 / 76.33	76.32 / 78.47
512	74.65 / 77.16	76.85 / 78.61	78.17 / 79.96

Even though ArcFace has shown its power in efficient and effective feature embedding, the original work introduces a version of the technique that could further improve the performance. In subcenter ArcFace [13], each class has K sub-centers set. Based on an L2 normalization on both feature embedding and all subcenters, we get the subclass-wise similarity scores after a matrix multiplication. Then, a max pooling step on these scores gives us the class-wise similarity score. In our setting, a given class is a Romanian county, which can have several distinctive subclasses/subclusters (e.g. different cities, towns, distinctive looking natural areas). Ideally, subcenter ArcFace would better separate the examples inside one geocell into well-defined clusters and, ultimately, improve the accuracy. Given the outcomes from Table VI, it seems that this subclustering helped, but without sufficient significance.

TABLE VI
COMPARISON OF ARCFACE VARIANTS ON CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY

Method	Accuracy (\uparrow)
ArcFace ($k = 1$)	74.23
Subcenter ArcFace ($k = 5$)	74.71

B. Image Geolocalization through Regression

Instead of predicting the correct state/county, the model could instead output a best guess regarding the geographical coordinates for the input sample. This was performed in 2 ways. On one hand, a model was trained with a regression objective, minimizing the mean squared error between the predicted and ground truth coordinates. On the other hand, after training a model with the ArcFace objective, the most similar database example to a test input will give its coordinates instead of its class as the final prediction. The Arcface retrieval version vastly outperforms standard regression (Table

TABLE VII
METHOD COMPARISON FOR REGRESSING THE ACTUAL GEOGRAPHICAL POSITION

Method	% @ km (\uparrow)			Error (km)	
	1	30	80	Mean	Median
Standard regression	0.5	2.56	35.62	117.45	89.87
ArcFace coordinate sharing	8.35	49.77	80.65	61.49	30.20

VIII). To achieve comparable results, the latter would probably need a larger and more geographically dense training set.

Due to the nature of our classification problem and the use of administrative boundaries (rather than physical boundaries between different types of landscape, which would produce more significant visual changes), the testing samples near the county border can become harder to classify. To test this hypothesis, we evaluated the same model on different testing sets: the full one (19,184 items) and a filtered one (15,408 items), the latter including only samples that are at least 3 kilometers away from any county border. We also report the performance on samples that are at most 3 kilometers away. Even though the buffer distance is relatively small, we already observe an improvement in the predictive performance on the far-from-border instances and a reduced accuracy for the near-border ones (Table VIII), confirming our hypothesis and intuition that there is increased ambiguity near administrative boundaries.

TABLE VIII
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON ON TEST SET SAMPLES SPLIT BY PROXIMITY TO GEOCELL/COUNTY BOUNDARIES

Subset	Accuracy (\uparrow)
Full	74.71
Far-from-border	76.06
Near-border	67.82

At inference time, we could tradeoff between acceptance rate (i.e. alternative for coverage) and accuracy by employing confidence-based techniques. For standard classification, we select/accept a prediction if the softmax-derived probability is greater than a certain threshold. At the same time, for ArcFace, we accept a prediction if the cosine similarity between the query and the most similar reference item is greater than a threshold. In both cases, each threshold value produces a coverage-accuracy pair and, by sweeping over a range a values, a coverage-accuracy plot. Figure 4 presents these plots for ArcFace and standard classification. We can observe that, for a given coverage, ArcFace displays a better accuracy (e.g. 85% accuracy with 85% accepted samples compared to 81% accuracy for Classifier).

C. Qualitative Examples

Some examples for geolocation are given in Fig. 5 and 6 (ground truth - Bucharest - good predictions) and in Fig. 7 (ground truth - Constanta - wrong predictions).

Fig. 4. Main methods of this project compared with respect to how accuracy changes when targeting a certain coverage/acceptance rate.

Fig. 5. Good prediction for Bucharest.

D. Comparison with Existing Methods

In order to compare results for image based geolocalization we considered several existing models. StreetCLIP [14] predictions are derived from doing zero-shot classification using cosine similarity between the image embedding and a text prompt template (eg. A Street View photo in the region of county in Romania) that closely matches the one used in training. The predicted county is the one that has the highest similarity score. Qwen2.5VL [15] has been fine-tuned on the GeoguessRO data, using all 4 images for one location and the prompt is: Which Romanian county best fits the given images? Despite the claims of planet-scale pretraining for StreetCLIP or various training schedules used for fine-tuning Qwen, the performance is significantly lower in comparison to our models (Table IX). For StreetCLIP, possible explanations for the failure in this benchmark would be the over-reliance on an exact prompt template (we omitted the city information due to the lack of this metadata) or insufficient Romanian-based samples in the original training mix. For Qwen2.5VL, more hyperparameter tuning and an extended training time would most likely be needed.

Fig. 6. Good prediction for Constanta.

Fig. 7. Wrong prediction for Constanta.

TABLE IX
EVALUATION OF VARIOUS EXISTING SOLUTIONS ON THE GEOGUESSRO BENCHMARK. * = ZERO-SHOT EVALUATION, ** = FINE-TUNED MODEL

Method	Top-1	Top-2	Top-5
StreetCLIP* [23]	2.38	—	—
Qwen2.5VL** [24]	6.95	—	—
Best classifier (Ours)	78.17	88.52	95.39
Best ArcFace (Ours)	79.96	89.03	95.86

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a system for image based geolocalization by combining image classification and regression, specifically with applications in law enforcement and digital investigations. Using a new image dataset from Romania of reference images and a strong augmentation pipeline it is created a system that is robust to adversarial interventions.

As future work will do explicit error analysis and statistical validation. Future studies should also report statistical tests and confidence intervals to strengthen the robustness of the results. Also, we will use synthetic data obtained from high-performance image editing models. Moreover, if we shift our focus towards the entertainment side, we can extend the system to design an agent that will be capable of playing a Moving game, either through API interaction or through GUI screenshots. Such an agent will need to possess specific skills that would allow it to have better guesses when moving instead of locked in a single position (e.g. which direction to follow at an intersection, which object of interest to zoom in on, etc.).

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